

Replication Package for: “Housing Prices and Credit Constraints in Competitive Search”

This replication package accompanies Díaz, Jerez and Rincón-Zapatero. (forthcoming). “Housing Prices and Credit Constraints in Competitive Search”. The Economic Journal.

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Instructions

This file describes the files contained in the folder **3 Replication Package**. There are two folders:

- **Data_SCF** contains the raw data and the Matlab files needed to obtain the targets from the Survey of Consumer Finances, <https://www.federalreserve.gov/econres/scfindex.htm>.
- **Codes** contains the codes to replicate Figure 3 and Tables 4 to 6 in the paper.

The rest of this **readme file** describes the contents of each folder.

NOTE: Figures 1 and 2 in the paper manually created as they are illustrations of the theory and the mechanics of the main algorithm. The code does not generate them.

Data availability and provenance statements

Statement about rights

- I certify that the author(s) of the manuscript have legitimate access to and permission to use the data used in this manuscript.
- I certify that the author(s) of the manuscript have documented permission to redistribute/publish the data contained within this replication package. Appropriate permission are documented in the [LICENSE.txt](#) file.

Summary of availability

- All data **are** publicly available.
- Some data **cannot be made** publicly available.
- **No data can be made** publicly available.

Details on data source

Internal calibration of the model parameters uses as targets data from the Survey of Consumer Finances <https://www.federalreserve.gov/econres/scfindex.htm>.

Data of Survey of Consumer Finances were downloaded from the U.S. Board of Governors of the Federal reserve System (2019). The data are in the public domain. Data can be downloaded from <https://www.federalreserve.gov/econres/scfindex.htm>, select the wave, then download. Only a part of the data of each wave is needed in this paper. A copy of the data needed is provided as part of this archive in .txt format.

Data.Name	Data.Files	Location	Provided	Citation
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Survey of Consumer Finances 1989	Rawdata_1989.txt	3 Replication package/Data_SCF	TRUE	Board of Governors (2019)
Survey of Consumer Finances 1992	Rawdata_1992.txt	3 Replication package/Data_SCF	TRUE	Board of Governors (2019)
Survey of Consumer Finances 1995	Rawdata_1995.txt	3 Replication package/Data_SCF	TRUE	Board of Governors (2019)
Survey of Consumer Finances 1998	Rawdata_1998.txt	3 Replication package/Data_SCF	TRUE	Board of Governors (2019)
Survey of Consumer Finances 2001	Rawdata_2001.txt	3 Replication package/Data_SCF	TRUE	Board of Governors (2019)
Survey of Consumer Finances 2004	Rawdata_2004.txt	3 Replication package/Data_SCF	TRUE	Board of Governors (2019)
Survey of Consumer Finances 2007	Rawdata_2007.txt	3 Replication package/Data_SCF	TRUE	Board of Governors (2019)
Consumer Price Index	cpi_index.txt	3 Replication package/Data_SCF	TRUE	Bureau of Labor Statistics (2019)

Computational requirements

Software requirements

Matlab (code was run with Matlab Release 2022b). It uses its main toolboxes such as

- Optimization toolbox.

Memory and runtime requirements

Summary

Approximate time needed to reproduce the analyses on a standard (2022) desktop machine:

- <10 minutes
- 10-60 minutes
- 1-2 hours
- 2-8 hours
- 8-24 hours
- 1-3 days
- 3-14 days
- > 14 days
- Not feasible to run on a desktop machine, as described below.

Details

This code was run in an iMac 2015, 16 GB RAM, IOS 12.6.3 with Matlab version 2022b. Computation took 76 minutes. However, in a MacBook Pro 16 GB RAM, IOS 13.4.1 with Matlab version 2023b computation time fell to 32 minutes.

INSTRUCTIONS: Identifying hardware and OS can be obtained through a variety of ways: Some of these details can be found as follows:

- (Windows) by right-clicking on “This PC” in File Explorer and choosing “Properties”
- (Mac) Apple-menu > “About this Mac”
- (Linux) see code in [tools/linux-system-info.sh](#)

Description of program/codes

- Programs in **3 Replication package/Data_SCF** will use raw data and find calibration targets used in Section 4.3.2.
- Programs in **3 Replication package/Codes** contains the code to simulate the benchmark and additional economies studied in the paper.

Description of the data and code in folder Data_SCF

The raw data for each SCF wave is included in “rawdata_wave.txt”. The needed Matlab code to compute the targets is

- “main_facts.m”: script file that cleans the data and extracts the data pertaining to working age households. This function calls:
 - “per.m”: function that calculates percentiles.
 - “ineq.m”: function that calculates inequality statistics.

The targets are written in an Excel file called “targets_paper_search”, as a csv file and as a Matlab table. The three output files are located in the folder where “main_facts.m”, “per.m” and “ineq.m” are located.

The output is saved in **3 Replication package/Data_SCF/Targets_paper_search.csv**
3 Replication package/Data_SCF/Targets_paper_search.xlsx

Description of the code in folder Codes

This folder contains the code to simulate the benchmark and additional economies studied in the paper. Specifically, this code takes as inputs the data shown in Tables 1, 2 and 3 and obtains Figure 3, Tables 4, 5 and 6. The code follows Appendix F in the paper.

Figure/Table	Program	Location	Line Number	Output	Notes
Figure 3	Main_code.m	3 Replication package/Codes	138	Figure_3a.png Figure_3b.png Figure_3c.png	Up to here, the code generates the benchmark steady state, saves it for Tables 4, 5 and 6 and plots policy functions in Figure 3. Located in 3 Replication package/Codes
Table 4	Main_code.m	3 Replication package/Codes	201	Table_4.csv	Located in 3 Replication package/Codes
Table 5	Main_code.m	3 Replication package/Codes	251	Table_5.csv	Located in 3 Replication package/Codes
Table 6	Main_code.m	3 Replication package/Codes	320	Table_6.csv	Located in 3 Replication package/Codes

The script file “main_code.m” loads all parameter values (whose values are shown in Tables 1, 2 and 3 in the paper) and obtains Figure 3, Tables 4 to 6 of the paper. Main files called:

- “find_eqm_search.m”: function that finds the equilibrium of the search economy for a particular value of the down payment parameter and price \bar{p} . It uses the algorithm described in Section F.4. Its mechanics is illustrated in Figure 2. For each value for \bar{p} “find_eqm_search.m” calls the file “get_aggregates.m” finds the steady state main aggregates. It calls
 - “get_policies.m” finds the policy functions following the algorithm outlined in Appendix F.2.
 - “get_cdfs.m” finds the stationary distribution of owners, renters and buyers, as described in Appendix B, Section F.3 and equations (8)–(9).
 - “get_buyers_sellers.m” This function gets the sum of sellers needed to satisfy the demand given by ψ_b , which is the distribution of buyers over wealth levels as well as

statistics of the distribution of equilibrium prices and vacancies and shown in Equation (9).

- “**get_policies.m**” solves the household’s problem as described in Section E.2.3. It uses the following functions:
 - “**get_pol_c0_renter.m**” finds the initial guess for the renter’s financial assets policy function. It assumes that renters never participate in the frictional housing market.
 - “**get_pol_c0_owner.m**” finds the initial guess for the owner’s financial assets policy function. It assumes that owners never receive a mismatching shock.
 - “**get_pol_p**” calculates the choice of submarket that solves buyer’s problem shown in Equation (4) in Section 3.1.3. It uses “fzero” from Matlab and functions
 - “**foc_p.m**”, the First Order Condition of the problem shown in Equation (4),
 - “**eqm_prob.m**” is the indifference curve of intermediaries, which gives the probabilities of selling and buying for any given price.
 - “**get_pol_c_renter.m**” uses the Euler equation of the problem shown in Equation (3) to find the optimal choice of financial assets for renters. It uses the optimal choice of housing price found in “get_pol_p.m”. The algorithm is described in Appendix F.2.3.
 - “**get_pol_c_owner.m**” performs the same task for owners. It solves the problem shown in Equation (2).
 - “**vfi_step.m**” conducts the Value Function Iteration step and it is called by “get_pol_c_renter” and “get_pol_c_owner”.
 - Auxiliar functions: “**felicity.m**” and “**der_felicity_inv.m**” calculate the felicity function and its partial derivative with respect to non-housing consumption. “**eqm_prob.m**” calculates the buying and selling probability for each price $p \geq \bar{p}$.
- “**get_cdfs.m**” computes a finer grid of financial assets and an initial distribution of financial assets for owners and renters. It assumes that immigrants come with zero financial assets. It uses the functions:
 - “**get_cdf_afternoon.m**” gets the measure of non-owners (buyers) before the frictional housing market opens, as shown in Section (3.3).
 - “**get_cdf_night.m**” gets the distribution of owners and renters after the frictional market has closed, as shown in Section (3.3).
 - “**interp_cdf.m**” interpolates to find the cdf of a particular variable.
- **The Walrasian economy:** Table 4 reports the steady state of three economies with search and matching frictions. This economy has no frictions and there is a unique housing price. The files needed to find the steady state of this economy have the same names than in the search economy but for the suffix “**_walras**” appended to the name of the file.

References

Board of Governors of the Federal Reserve System (2019). ‘Survey of Consumer Finances’, <https://www.federalreserve.gov/econres/scfindex.htm>.